
A DFT analysis of the relationships between electronic structure and inhibition of aurora kinase A and epidermal growth factor receptor kinase by a set of N^4 -phenyl substituted-7H-pyrrolo[2,3-d]pyrimidin-4-amines

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Abstract A quantum-chemical structure-activity study is carried out for the inhibition of aurora kinase A and epidermal growth factor receptor kinase by a group of N^4 -phenylsubstituted-7H-pyrrolo[2,3-d]pyrimidin-4-amines. The Klopman-Peradejordi-Gómez method was employed. Statistically significant relationships between the variation of the inhibitory capacity of a group of N^4 -phenylsubstituted-7H-pyrrolo[2,3-d]pyrimidin-4-amines against aurora kinase A and epidermal growth factor receptor kinase and the variation of the values of several local atomic reactivity indices were obtained. The results are presented in the form of a partial pharmacophore that could be useful in the synthesis of new and more powerful molecules.

Keywords Aurora kinase A, epidermal growth factor receptor kinase, QSAR, common skeleton, DFT, electronic structure, pharmacophore, KPG model, Klopman-Peradejordi-Gómez method

Introduction

Cancer is a group of diseases involving uncontrolled cell proliferation occurs in body. Antimitotic molecules, which disrupted mitotic spindle assembly, are usually used to treat almost all kinds of cancer. Kinase inhibitors play a critical role in creation of anti-cancer agents. Common targets for this strategy are Aurora kinase and Polo like kinase. Aurora kinase was identified in 1995 and is a member of the enzymes serine/threonine kinase family. It is involved in G2/M phase of the cell cycle and its regulation process is observed during the complete cell cycle. For more detailed information, see for example the review of Borisa and Bhatt [1]. Dysfunctional epidermal growth factor receptor kinase plays a role in tumor progression and angiogenesis in squamous cell carcinoma of the head and neck, non-small cell lung cancer and colorectal cancer[2]. Given the importance of these kinases for combating cancer, many chemical compounds have been synthesized and tested for inhibitory capacity [2-14].

Recently Kurup et al. published data about the inhibition of aurora kinase A (AURKA) and epidermal growth factor receptor kinase (EGFR) by a group of N^4 -phenylsubstituted-7H-pyrrolo[2,3-d]pyrimidin-4-amines [2]. In this paper we present the results of the application of the Klopman-Peradejordi- Gómez method for the search of relationships between electronic structure and inhibitory capacities of the abovementioned molecules.

Methods and Models

The Klopman-Peradejordi-Gómez (KPG) method belongs to the class of model-based methods. Since this model has been presented in several papers [15-25], we shall present here only its main lines of development and discuss below

only the results obtained here. Starting from the statistical-mechanical definition of the equilibrium constant, an expression relating this experimental value with several local atomic reactivity indices and orientational parameters was developed. Its application to several different molecules and receptors gave very good results (see [23, 26-43] and references therein). Its extension to all kinds of biological activities was very fruitful (see [40, 44-61] and references therein).

The molecules and inhibitory data against AURKA and EGFR were taken from a recent publication, and are presented in Fig. 1 and Table 1.

Figure 1: General formula of molecules used in this study

Table 1.

Mol.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	log(IC ₅₀)	log(IC ₅₀)
				AURKA	EGFR
1	H	H	H	0.75	2.41
2	H	Br	H	0.30	0.58
3	H	F	Cl	0.52	0.78
4	H	H	Cl	0.71	1.93
5	H	Cl	Cl	0.59	0.83
6	H	H	OMe	0.83	3.47
7	H	Br	Cl	0.51	0.56
8	H	H	Me	0.74	2.82
9	H	H	Br	0.71	2.10
10	H	Me	H	0.54	1.30
11	H	CF ₃	H	0.76	1.64
12	Cl	H	H	0.75	2.67
13	Me	H	H	0.93	3.09
14	H	H	Ph	1.87	----
15	H	H	OPh	1.12	2.05
16	H	H	CH ₂ Ph	0.70	1.80

Calculations

The electronic structure of all molecules was calculated within the Density Functional Theory (DFT) at the B3LYP/6-31G(d,p) level with full geometry optimization [62]. The Gaussian suite of programs was used [63]. The information needed to calculate the numerical values for the LARIs was obtained from the Gaussian results with the D-Cent-QSAR software [64]. All the electron populations smaller than or equal to 0.01 e were considered as zero. Negative electron populations coming from Mulliken Population Analysis [65] were corrected as usual [66]. Orientational parameters taken from published Tables or calculated in our Unit with the Steric software [67]. Since the resolution of the system of linear equations is not possible because we have not experimental data, we employed Linear Multiple Regression Analysis (LMRA) techniques to find the best solution. For each case, a matrix containing the dependent variable (log(IC₅₀) in this case) and the local atomic reactivity indices of all atoms of the common skeleton as independent variables was built. Regarding the local atomic reactivity indices depending on the MO (Fukui indices and superdelocalizabilities) we have employed only those associated with the frontier local molecular orbitals. The Statistica software was used for LMRA [68].

Figure 2: Common skeleton numbering

Results

An initial analysis of the common skeleton

Using the actual knowledge about molecular interactions, we can carry out a previous analysis of the common skeleton to propose several possible interactions. Figure 3 shows the main possible drug-site interactions. We may add C-H... π , lone pair... π and S... π interactions (Gómez-Jeria et al., unpublished). KPG method, in its statistical form, should confirm one or more of them.

Figure 3: Possible common skeleton-site interactions

Results for aurora kinase A inhibition (AURKA)

The best statistically significant equation obtained is the following:

$$\log(\text{IC}_{50}) = 1.32 - 2.76F_7(\text{LUMO}+2)^* + 1.81F_7(\text{HOMO}-1)^* \quad (1)$$

with $n=16$, $R=0.97$, $R^2=0.94$, $\text{adj-}R^2=0.93$, $f(2,13)=102.7$ ($p<0.000001$) and a standard error of the estimate of 0.09. No outliers were detected and no residuals fall outside the $\pm 2\sigma$ limits. Here, $F_7(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$ is the Fukui index of the third lowest empty MO localized on atom 7 and $F_7(\text{HOMO}-1)^*$ is the Fukui index of the second highest occupied MO localized on atom 7. Tables 2 and 3 show, respectively, the beta coefficients, the results of the t-test for significance of coefficients and the matrix of squared correlation coefficients for the variables of Eq. 1. There are no significant internal correlations between independent variables (Table 3). Figure 3 displays the plot of observed vs. calculated $\log(\text{IC}_{50})$.

Table 2: Beta coefficients and t-test for significance of coefficients in Eq. 1

	Beta	t(13)	p-level
$F_7(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$	-1.10	-14.20	<0.000001
$F_7(\text{HOMO}-1)^*$	0.41	5.30	<0.0001

Table 3: Matrix of squared correlation coefficients for the variables in Eq. 1

	$F_7(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$	$F_7(\text{HOMO}-1)^*$
$F_7(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$	1.00	
$F_7(\text{HOMO}-1)^*$	0.24	1.00

Figure 4: Plot of predicted vs. observed $\log(\text{IC}_{50})$ values (Eq. 1). Dashed lines denote the 95% confidence interval. The associated statistical parameters of Eq. 1 indicate that this equation is statistically significant and that the variation of the numerical values of a group of two local atomic reactivity indices of atoms of the common skeleton explains about 93% of the variation of $\log(\text{IC}_{50})$. Figure 4, spanning about 1.6 orders of magnitude, shows that there is a good correlation of observed versus calculated values.

Results for epidermal growth factor receptor kinase inhibition (EGFR)

The best statistically significant equation obtained is the following:

$$\log(\text{IC}_{50}) = -10.03 - 6.90S_{12}^E(\text{HOMO})^* - 7.77S_3^E(\text{HOMO}-2)^* + 4.38F_9(\text{LUMO}+2)^* + 15.38Q_{11} \quad (2)$$

with $n=14$, $R=0.99$, $R^2=0.98$, $\text{adj-}R^2=0.98$, $F(4,9)=191.06$ ($p < 0.00000x$) and a standard error of estimate of 0.12. No outliers were detected and no residuals fall outside the $\pm 2\sigma$ limits. Here, $S_{12}^E(\text{HOMO})^*$ is the electrophilic superdelocalizability of the highest occupied MO localized on atom 12, $S_3^E(\text{HOMO}-2)^*$ is the electrophilic superdelocalizability of the third highest occupied MO localized on atom 3, $F_9(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$ is the Fukui index of the third lowest empty MO localized on atom 9 and Q_{11} is the net charge of atom 11. Tables 4 and 5 show, respectively, the beta coefficients, the results of the t-test for significance of coefficients and the matrix of squared correlation coefficients for the variables of Eq. 2. There are no significant internal correlations between independent variables (Table 4). Figure 5 displays the plot of observed vs. calculated $\log(\text{IC}_{50})$.

Table 4: Beta coefficients and t-test for significance of coefficients in Eq. 2

	Beta	t(9)	p-level
$S_{12}^E(\text{HOMO})^*$	-0.87	-21.06	<0.000001
$S_3^E(\text{HOMO-2})^*$	-0.53	-14.31	<0.000001
$F_9(\text{LUMO+2})^*$	0.22	5.65	<0.0003
Q_{11}	0.17	4.24	<0.002

Table 5: Matrix of squared correlation coefficients for the variables in Eq. 2

	$S_{12}^E(\text{HOMO})^*$	$S_3^E(\text{HOMO-2})^*$	$F_9(\text{LUMO+2})^*$	Q_{11}
$S_{12}^E(\text{HOMO})^*$	1.00			
$S_3^E(\text{HOMO-2})^*$	0.01	1.00		
$F_9(\text{LUMO+2})^*$	0.08	0.04	1.00	
Q_{11}	0.12	0.01	0.02	1.00

Figure 5: Plot of predicted vs. observed $\log(\text{IC}_{50})$ values (Eq. 2). Dashed lines denote the 95% confidence interval. The associated statistical parameters of Eq. 2 indicate that this equation is statistically significant and that the variation of the numerical values of a group of four local atomic reactivity indices of atoms of the common skeleton explains about 98% of the variation of $\log(\text{IC}_{50})$. Figure 5, spanning about 3 orders of magnitude, shows that there is a good correlation of observed versus calculated values. Note that when a local atomic reactivity index of an inner occupied MO (i.e., HOMO-1 and/or HOMO-2) or of a higher vacant MO (LUMO+1 and/or LUMO+2) appears in one equation, it implies that the remaining of the upper occupied MOs (for example, if HOMO-2 appears, upper means HOMO-1 and HOMO) or the remaining of the empty MOs (for example, if LUMO+1 appears, lower means the LUMO) contribute to the interaction. Their nonappearance in the equation only means that the variation of their numerical values is not statistically significant.

Local molecular orbitals

Tables 6 and 7 show the local molecular orbitals of atoms 3, 7, 9, 11 and 12.

Table 6: Local molecular orbitals of atoms 3, 7 and 9

Mol.	3(C)	7(C)	9(N)
1(55)	52σ54π55π-56π57π58π	51π54π55π-56π59π60π	52σ54π55π-56π57π58π
2(72)	70π71π72π-73π77π78π	70π71π72π-73π77π78π	70π71π72π-73π74π75π
3(67)	64σ66π67π-68π70π71π	65π66π67π-68π71π73π	64σ66π67π-68π69π70π
4(63)	61σ62π63π-64π66π67π	59π62π63π-64π67π69π	61σ62π63π-64π65π66π
5(71)	68σ70π71π-72π76π77π	69π70π71π-72π76π77π	68σ70π71π-72π74π76π
6(63)	61σ62π63π-64π65π66π	59π62π63π-64π67π68π	60π61σ62π-64π65π66π
7(80)	77σ79π80π-81π85π86π	78π79π80π-81π85π86π	78π79π80π-81π84π85π
8(59)	56σ58π59π-60π61π62π	55π58π59π-60π63π64π	56σ58π59π-60π61π62π
9(72)	70σ71π72π-73π77π78π	68π71π72π-73π77π78π	70σ71π72π-73π74π75π
10(59)	57π58π59π-60π61π62π	57π58π59π-60π63π64π	57π58π59π-60π61π62π
11(71)	69σ70π71π-72π73π75π	68π70π71π-72π75π76π	69σ70π71π-72π74π75π
12(63)	60σ62π63π-64π68π69π	61π62π63π-64π68π69π	61π62π63π-64π65π66π
13(59)	56σ58π59π-60π61π62π	57π58π59π-60π63π64π	57π58π59π-60π61π62π
14(75)	71σ74π75π-76π77π78π	71σ74π75π-76π77π78π	71σ74π75π-77π80π81π
15(79)	77π78π79π-80π84π85π	77π78π79π-80π84π85π	77π78π79π-80π82π83π
16(79)	77π78π79π-80π84π85π	77π78π79π-80π85π86π	77π78π79π-80π81π83π

Table 7: Local molecular orbitals of atoms 11 and 12

Mol.	11(C)	12(C)
1(55)	49π54π55π-56π57π58π	53π54π55π-56π57π58π
2(72)	70π71π72π-73π74π75π	70π71π72π-73π74π75π
3(67)	62π66π67π-68π69π70π	59π65π67π-68π69π70π
4(63)	58π62π63π-64π65π66π	60π62π63π-64π65π66π
5(71)	69π70π71π-72π73π74π	64σ69π71π-72π73π75σ
6(63)	60π62π63π-64π65π66π	60π62π63π-64π65π66π
7(80)	78π79π80π-81π82π83σ	75σ78π80π-81π82π83σ
8(59)	54π58π59π-60π61π62π	57π58π59π-60π61π62π
9(72)	64π71π72π-73π74π75π	69π71π72π-73π74π75π
10(59)	57π58π59π-60π61π62π	52σ57π59π-60π61π62π
11(71)	65π70π71π-72π73π74π	68π70π71π-72π73π74π
12(63)	61π62π63π-64π65π66π	61π62π63π-64π65π66π
13(59)	57π58π59π-60π61π62π	57π58π59π-60π61π62π
14(75)	72π74π75π-76π77π81π	72π73π75π-76π77π78π
15(79)	77π78π79π-80π81π82π	77π78π79π-80π81π82π
16(79)	77π78π79π-80π81π83π	76π78π79π-80π81π84π

Discussion

Discussion for aurora kinase A inhibition (AURKA)

Table 2 shows that the importance of variables in Eq. 1 is $F_7(\text{LUMO}+2)^* \gg F_7(\text{HOMO}-1)^*$. A high inhibitory activity is associated with high positive values of $F_7(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$ and small positive values of $F_7(\text{HOMO}-1)^*$. Table 6 shows that $(\text{HOMO}-1)_7^*$, HOMO_7^* , LUMO_7^* , $(\text{LUMO}+1)_7^*$ and $(\text{LUMO}+2)_7^*$ have a π nature. Atom 7 is a carbon in ring C (Fig. 2). A high value of $F_7(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$ indicates that atom interacts with an electron-rich center in the enzyme. Considering that $F_7(\text{LUMO}+1)^*$ and $F_7(\text{LUMO})^*$ should also participate in the interaction, it is possible to speculate that the center could be a carboxylate moiety or an aromatic ring. On the other hand, small positive values of $F_7(\text{HOMO}-1)^*$ are needed for better inhibitory activity. This means that $F_7(\text{HOMO}-1)^*$ and $F_7(\text{HOMO})^*$ are engaged in a repulsive interaction with occupied MOs of the enzyme, fact that is in agreement with

the requirements for the empty local MOs. All the suggestions are displayed in the partial 2D pharmacophore of Fig. 6.

Figure 6: Partial 2D pharmacophore for the inhibition of aurora kinase A by a set of N^4 -phenyl substituted-7H-pyrrolo[2,3-d]pyrimidin-4-amines

Discussion for the epidermal growth factor receptor kinase inhibition (EGFR)

Table 4 shows that the importance of variables in Eq. 2 is $S_{12}^E(\text{HOMO})^* > S_3^E(\text{HOMO}-2)^* > F_9(\text{LUMO}+2)^* > Q_{11}$. A high inhibitory activity is associated with small (negative) values for $S_{12}^E(\text{HOMO})^*$ and $S_3^E(\text{HOMO}-2)^*$, with small values of $F_9(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$ and with negative values of the net charge of atom 11. Atom 11 is a carbon located in ring A and bonded to the N atom linking rings A and B (Fig. 2). The net charge of this atom is positive in all molecules. We need to lower this charge to have a better activity. This can be done, for example, by attaching an electron-donor group to atoms 12, 13 and/or 15 (Fig. 2).

Atom 12 is a carbon located in ring A and bonded to atom 11 (Fig. 2). Table 7 shows that HOMO_{12}^* has a π character in all molecules. Small (negative) values for $S_{12}^E(\text{HOMO})^*$ can be obtained by diminishing the electronic density of this MO at atom 12, making more negative the energy of the MO or by both procedures simultaneously. Also, another possibility is changing the actual HOMO_{12}^* by an inner molecular MO. All these changes transform atom 12 in a bad electron donor. An electron-attractor group at positions 14 and/or 16 would subtract electrons from atom 12. Note that the conditions deduced for atom 12 are contradictory with a negative net charge on atom 11. Now, looking to Table 4 we may see that $S_{12}^E(\text{HOMO})^*$ is the most important variable in Eq. 2 and Q_{11} the less important one. Therefore, we may discard or the moment the conditions for atom 11 waiting for the appearance of new data of new derivatives. Therefore, atom 12 seems to behave a good electron acceptor. Atom 3 is a carbon in ring B and bonded to the N atom linking rings A and B (Fig. 2). Table 6 shows that $S_3^E(\text{HOMO}-2)^*$ has a π or σ character following the molecule. A high activity is associated with small (negative) values for $S_3^E(\text{HOMO}-2)^*$. Small values are obtained in the same way than we used for HOMO_{12}^* . We have analyzed also the plots (not shown here) of $\log(\text{IC}_{50})$ vs. $S_3^E(\text{HOMO}-1)^*$ and $\log(\text{IC}_{50})$ vs. $S_3^E(\text{HOMO})^*$. The plot of $\log(\text{IC}_{50})$ vs. $S_3^E(\text{HOMO}-1)^*$ shows that high activity is associated with low (negative) values for this index. But the plot of $\log(\text{IC}_{50})$ vs. $S_3^E(\text{HOMO})^*$ shows an opposite trend: a high activity is associated with high (negative) values of $S_3^E(\text{HOMO})^*$. Therefore, atom 3 behaves as an electron-acceptor. Atom 9 is nitrogen in ring C (Fig. 2). A high inhibitory activity is associated with small values of $F_9(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$. Table 6 shows that the three lowest empty local MOs of this atom have a π character. The plots of $F_9(\text{LUMO}+1)^*$ vs. $\log(\text{IC}_{50})$ and $F_9(\text{LUMO})^*$ vs. $\log(\text{IC}_{50})$ (not shown here) shows the same trend. On the other hand, $(\text{HOMO})_9^*$ has a π character in all molecules (Table 6). On this basis we suggest that atom 9 is acting as an electron donor. All the suggestions are displayed in the partial 2D pharmacophore of Fig. 7.

Figure 7: Partial 2D pharmacophore for the inhibition of epidermal growth factor receptor kinase A by a set of N^4 -phenyl substituted-7H-pyrrolo[2,3-d]pyrimidin-4-amines

In summary, we have obtained statistically significant relationships between the variation of the inhibitory capacity of a group of N^4 -phenylsubstituted-7H-pyrrolo[2,3-d]pyrimidin-4-amines against aurora kinase A and epidermal growth factor receptor kinase and the variation of the values of several local atomic reactivity indices of some atoms belonging to a common skeleton. These results are depicted in the corresponding partial pharmacophore that could be useful in the design of new and more powerful molecules.

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